

4.fcs
Ungated
22807

4.fcs
Nuclei
10146

5.fcs
Ungated
12403

5.fcs
Nuclei
3903

6.fcs
Ungated
22811

6.fcs
Nuclei
7394

A488_only.fcs
Ungated
20325

A488_only.fcs
Nuclei
15421

DAPI_only.fcs
Ungated
47507

DAPI_only.fcs
Nuclei
30959

